

The effects of consumer's ethnocentrism on consumer's purchase in Marketplace

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Abstract

The purpose of this study was to investigate the impact of consumer's ethnocentrism on consumer's towards domestic and foreign products. However, this may not be the case for marketers, because of the influence of strong feelings of national pride on behaviour of the consumers. Measures of consumer ethnocentrism may provide marketers with the information necessary to target consumers who do not allow nationalistic feelings to influence product quality evaluation and purchase behaviour. Also, the necessity of the product to consumers may provide marketers with clues on which products will be accepted in the marketplace. Results are derived from primary data collected from a consumer sample from those who appear to not be overly ethnocentric, are willing to purchase products from other countries, but will be more likely to buy certain products because of the reputation these products and brands from specific countries have acquired. Thus, data was collected through a questionnaire which was distributed online to a representative sample, consisting of 150 individuals. Data was analyzed using the SPSS software. Factor analysis and Spearman correlation coefficient were used to test the research hypotheses. Study results show that the consumer's ethnocentric tendencies are positively related to consumer's purchase domestic products and negatively related to products. This means that ethnocentric consumers may have a more positive attitude toward purchasing products they deem necessary as opposed to unnecessary products, such as luxury items. Implications of the findings are discussed and directions for future research are provided.

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